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INTEGRATED LEARNING: INTEGRATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE AND FINE ARTS

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Annotation: The authors of this article focus on the fact that interdisciplinary integration in teaching a foreign language is one of the conditions for the successful acquisition and application of a foreign language in professional, social and cultural activities. This article demonstrates that the correct and skillful use of interdisciplinary courses, as well as the educational potential of academic disciplines, is of great importance in the modern educational process.

Key words: interdisciplinary integration, university student, foreign language, history, fine arts, language features.

The main task of the modern education system is the formation and development of an educated, creative, competent and competitive personality capable of living in a dynamically developing environment. Human education has always been a difficult task. Today's problems make this process even more difficult.

Integrated learning in the educational process is one of the important and modern problems. Its relevance is dictated by the new social demands presented to the school, secondary specialized educational institutions (colleges) and higher educational institutions (university). The modern education system is aimed at the formation of a highly educated, intellectually developed personality with a holistic view of the picture of the world [1]. The development of the education system is greatly influenced by changes in political, economic and social life. The society simultaneously faces the problem of preparing students for cultural, professional and personal communication both within their own country and (in the context of a globalized world) with representatives of other countries, when culture, traditions, and language are not identical. And one of the reasons for the fragmentation of the worldview of students is seen in subject disunity, while in the modern world tendencies towards economic, political and cultural integration prevail.

Integration [lat. integration – connection] is the unification of disparate parts into a

whole, deep interpenetration, merging in one educational material of generalized knowledge in a particular area [4].

The dictionary of modern pedagogical terms gives the following interpretation: integration is a natural way of knowing oneself and the world around, which is expressed in a combination of aesthetic, cognitive, historical-genetic, social and functional aspects [10].

An integrated lesson is one of the innovations of modern methodology. An integrated lesson is a special type of lesson that combines learning simultaneously in two (or more) disciplines while studying one topic, in which the leading discipline is distinguished, acting as an integrator, and an auxiliary discipline that contributes to deepening, expanding, clarifying the material of the leading discipline [2; 3; 9; 13].

The concept of "integration" can have two meanings: (1) the creation of a holistic view of the world around schoolchildren; (2) finding a common platform for convergence of knowledge.

The integration of subjects in general education schools and universities is one of the areas of active search for new pedagogical solutions that contribute to the improvement and development of the creative potential of teaching staff and teachers in order to more effectively and reasonably influence students.

Integrated lessons can combine a variety of disciplines, both in their entirety, and

including only certain components of the content and methods. Teachers resort to integrated lessons in the following cases:

- if duplication of the same material is found in curricula and textbooks;
- with a time limit for studying the topic and the desire to use ready-made content from a parallel discipline;
- in the study of interscientific and generalized categories, laws, principles;
- when demonstrating a wider field of manifestation of the phenomenon under study, which goes beyond the scope of the subject under study;
- when creating a problematic, developing methodology for teaching a subject [9].

At each stage of education, integration helps to solve certain educational tasks: (1) the formation of the student's cognitive interest and broadening their horizons; (2) knowledge of the world in its diversity and unity; - development of the potential of students, logic, thinking, communication skills; (3) formation of abilities for active cognition of the surrounding reality; (4) the formation of a socially active creative personality [5].

A foreign language is open to the use of knowledge from other fields and sciences, so it has many "points" of contact with fine arts and history. Acquaintance with the culture of the country of the language being studied (holidays, traditions, costumes, life of the people, etc.) can be successfully combined with the development of artistic and creative skills in compiling hand-made magazines, colorful collages, creating toys and paintings. You can develop speech and language skills in the process of designing holiday cards, posters, studying paintings by artists, architectural landmarks and other types of fine art. Thus, students strengthen language knowledge and skills in the field of graphics and painting, spelling and phonetics, vocabulary and grammar of the English language. For the purpose of a deeper and more creative mastering of speech skills, a teacher of fine arts can provide methodological support to

a foreign language teacher in selecting works of fine art for lessons. In short, through integrated learning, it is possible to form a certain style of thinking in students so that they feel confident in the modern world and can realize their abilities.

Recently, teachers often use non-traditional or non-standard forms of the lesson. These are, for example, seminar lessons, lectures, competitions, travel, theatrical lessons, conference classes, fairy tale lessons and more. In such a lesson, students learn to understand the relationship of all types of arts, history, linguistics and other subjects that sometimes do not overlap with each other [4].

From the point of view of research, interdisciplinary integration is the complementarity of one academic subject with another, and the purpose of this process is the synthesis of interrelated ideas about various phenomena of social life and the material world [3].

Interdisciplinary integration in teaching foreign languages allows you to form, develop and educate a versatile personality. The integration of knowledge from various fields of knowledge in the organization of training allows you to link into a single chain all the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in the process of studying various disciplines, which allows students to form an algorithm for obtaining new knowledge that allows them to subconsciously identify these connections [5].

The purpose of interdisciplinary integration in the study of a foreign language (history, art) is to form in students an algorithm for obtaining new knowledge (related to other sciences) in the study of a foreign language.

We consider interdisciplinary integration in two aspects: as internal (intra-subject) and external (connection of a subject - a foreign language with another subject, for example, history and fine arts).

A more accurate and voluminous definition of integration is given in the work of S.V. Kulnevich and T.T. Lakotsenina "Analysis of

the modern lesson": "Integration is a deep interpenetration, merging, as far as possible, in one educational material of generalized knowledge in a particular area." There are three levels of integration: (1) intra-subject - integration of concepts within individual academic subjects; (2) interdisciplinary - the synthesis of facts, concepts, principles, etc. two or more disciplines, which should be used by the teacher when preparing an integrated lesson; (3) transdisciplinary - synthesis of components of the main and additional content of education.

The use of techniques that allow the formation of both such methods of integration in foreign language lessons are very relevant, since they allow the use of laws, theories, methods of one academic discipline when studying another. Such a structure of systematization of the material leads to the formation of a general picture of the world among students, interdisciplinary connections lead to an increase in practical and scientific-theoretical training of students, form communication skills [1].

When analyzing an integrated lesson, you can use the following scheme:

1. The object of integration (culture, science, local history, people, technology, etc.).
2. Content and integration components. What academic disciplines are in it included? What is the mix of old, classic, and new, basic and additional, disciplines in the process of integration?
3. The direction and volume of integrable objects, in what way it is expressed: in creation of a new academic subject; in the creation of a cycle (block) periodically repeated lessons; creating single integrative lessons?
4. Level (stage) of content integration in a course or lesson: an organically unified, holistic new structure; parallel existence in one lesson or program of various layers of material; stage of transition from a parallel connection of material to an integral new

structure?

5. Theme of the integrative lesson, problem, goal. novelty level. Has the systematization of students' knowledge, the formation of a holistic view of the subject been achieved?

6. The activities of the teacher and students in preparation for the integrative lesson.

Is this lesson spontaneous or is it the result of careful student and teacher preparation? What independent work should the students have done before the lesson; its purpose, scope, character? Do these lessons make it easier for students to learn, or do they make life difficult for students?

7. Forms of conducting an integrative lesson, types of activities of teachers and students. Do they combine reasonably, do they lead to the goal?

8. Cooperation of teachers at the integrative level.

9. The results of students' activities in the integrated lesson. Did they create a single (integrated) idea of the problem; the breadth of their horizons; culture of judgments, their argumentation; the degree of confidence in the outcome of the discussion of the problem; a culture of speech; emotional involvement.

If we are talking about internal integration, it is important to note that any language is a unique, unique national or international system of signs. The way of life, cultural heritage, traditions of different nations are reflected in the structure of languages. Each society has certain norms of behavior, rules that are reflected in the structure of the language, which are accepted by a certain people, this is the ethnocultural model of self-expression [1]. It is different within the cultural and territorial national units. Linguistic features of all peoples reflect national and cultural differences, the history of the nation, the stages of development. Comparing the cultural and linguistic norms of different ethnic groups, one can see the singular (special) and the general in their application. The language culture

mastered by a person makes it possible to accept norms, orders, and even a specific model of behavior, misunderstanding of which leads to misunderstanding in verbal and non-verbal communication. The external integration of knowledge of various sciences is based on the fact that familiarizing students with the culture and knowledge of another people is the main principle of teaching foreign languages. It makes learning a foreign language more interesting. The use of literary, journalistic, scientific and folklore material helps to quickly comprehend the language on the example of scientific and cultural knowledge.

Forms of the educational process in which various levels of integration are manifested:

1. Structures in which several items are combined.
2. Blocking of different sections.
3. The study of one topic based on two or more subjects.
4. A course that combines knowledge based on generalized operations of thinking.

Integration levels:

Thematic - two or three subjects reveal one topic. The character is illustrative and explanatory.

Problematic - students solve one problem with the possibilities of a number of subjects.

Conceptual - the concept is considered by various subjects in the aggregate of all their means and methods.

Theoretical - philosophical interpenetration of various theories.

Dialectical level - involves the use of concepts and principles borrowed from different fields of knowledge, the synthesis of competing theories.

Implementation of integrated links in the lesson.

Integrated lessons require the mandatory development of students' creative activity, develop the potential of students, encourage active knowledge of the surrounding reality, to comprehend and find cause-and

-effect relationships, to develop their personality and communication skills.

The structure of integrated lessons differs from classical ones in clarity, compactness, conciseness, logical interdependence of educational material at each stage of the lesson, and a large informative capacity of the material.

The structure of the integrated-synchronized course allows teachers of different subjects to unite in creative groups to work together on related topics. Thus, introducing students to geometric activity, through integration with the subject of fine arts, in the process of which students master the skills of spatial, constructive, metric, intuitive, logical, symbolic activity and develop the creative potential of the individual, her ability to self-realization.

Integration results for students:

1. Increases the space for the development of creative and cognitive activity.
2. Allows you to implement an individual educational trajectory of learning.
3. Expands the subject of the studied material.
4. Demonstrates abilities not required by mainstream education.
5. Increases the range of the studied material.
6. Increases the role of independent work.
7. Realizes the best personal qualities.

Integration results for an educational institution:

1. Adequacy to modern requirements of education and upbringing;
2. Combining the efforts of different specialists in solving common problems;
3. Wide range of activities;
4. Emergence of new development prospects;
5. Obtaining a high-quality pedagogical result.

Recommendations:

To successfully conduct integrated classes, you must:

- systematic implementation of integrated classes once a week;

- the teacher's enthusiasm and awareness of the importance of the problem;
- incubation of the idea, in the process of which the further development of the content takes place;
- selection of technical equipment;
- systematic analysis of the integrated lesson in order to track the result for planning work in joint activities with children and in work with parents on this topic.

The idea of integration is most successfully implemented in the lessons of literature and fine arts: a text in a foreign language about the history and culture of the language being studied contributes to a vivid and imaginative perception of reality, and artistic creativity makes it possible to express one's attitude to a literary work in an accessible form for the student, developing attention and imagination. At present, three main forms of student organization have been established in the classroom:

The frontal form of organization of learning is expressed in the fact that all students perform the same tasks.

The group form of organizing the work of schoolchildren involves dividing the work into groups of several people, where each group performs its task.

An individual form of organization of work is the fulfillment by each student of a different task.

In the methodology of teaching integrated lessons, collective activity is defined as a method of summarizing the knowledge of students obtained during a cycle of lessons united by a single topic. The inclusion of an integrated lesson of collective activity in the calendar-thematic plan can be caused by preparations for the holiday. If the collective activity is aimed at decorating the interior of the school, then the main requirement in the work is quality and fast deadlines. In these lessons, as a rule, joint-sequential work, or joint-individual work. The main reason is the development of an objective assessment of one's abilities, dissatisfaction with the low results of creative activity.

If the result of individual activity does not satisfy some children, then the result of collective work exceeds his expectations. Unlike individual creativity, collective creativity, as a rule, has a practical and socially significant result.

The use in practice of integrated lessons with various forms of collective activity enables students to realize their social significance, spiritual beauty and nobility of actions, and school "obligation", as in a fairy tale, turns into a process of collective search, collective creativity and the formation of the child's personality.

Students become more active in the classroom, more confident in their abilities, their interaction with peers improves, more and more often they take the initiative to decorate the school for the holidays and participate in regional and city exhibitions.

The format of the game played is synthetic not only from a formal point of view. Including elements of the communicative-ethnographic and socio-cultural approaches, nevertheless, we bring to the fore the linguistic and cultural approach. Firstly, the class receives basic information on the study area of the student. The game uses a large amount of illustrative material (maps, photographs, pictures) to form a clear idea of the country of the language being studied. Secondly, the game format combines several forms of work: team work (oral answers to questions) and individual work (filling in tables); lecture (representation of the countries-teams by the teacher) and independent (solving crossword puzzles); intellectual (performing grammar and vocabulary exercises) and physical (a task related to an outdoor game). Thirdly, students are given the opportunity to practice the language in writing and orally, as well as training in the perception of English speech by ear, which is focused on developing the speaking and understanding skills necessary for learning a foreign language. Thus, such a lesson or extracurricular activity can serve as an example of studying the culture of a country in the format of an ed-

educational game, the main value of which is fair to consider that children learn to extract the necessary information on their own, in this case, answers to questions. The use of cultural material in the study of a foreign language, history and fine arts is necessary. With its help, if I may say so, the "territory" or "space" where the language is realized is demonstrated. Without a doubt, students are aware that a foreign language, like a native language, belongs to a certain country, and it is used, first of all, for communication between people. But the tongue cannot be touched. It, in comparison with objects of culture, is intangible. It is difficult for a person to feel and understand something alien if it cannot be seen or felt tactilely. National culture is that element that represents the country, which helps to "touch" the language, acting as its material carrier.

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